

RAL Ozone Profile Algorithm Product User Guide

Version 2.2

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1	0	01/04/2015	Added section about use of square AKs and separated out information about a useful function into a further appendix
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1. Nadir Profiles from the RAL Ozone Profile Scheme

1.1. L2 Product

This note describes the details of this RAL ozone profile dataset, including pertinent attributes of the data and algorithm used. The ozone profile retrieval scheme has been developed through funding primarily from the UK National Centre for Earth Observation (NCEO, www.nceo.ac.uk) and ESA Climate Change Initiative (CCI), with full mission processing support from EU Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) and UK Earth Observation Climate Information Service (EOCIS). For a full technical description of the retrieval algorithm used please refer to the full ATBD [available from <http://www.esa-ozone-cci.org/?q=documents#>], or Miles *et al.*, (2014) for algorithm and validation information. Richards *et al.*, (2013) is a good example of where this product has been used to qualify and assess the ozone in the lower troposphere as predicted by a chemistry transport model, which was then used for a radiative forcing study.

1.2. Data Processing and Parameters

NCDF files are produced by the RAL nadir profile ozone scheme for GOME aboard ERS-2 (06/1995-06/2011), SCIAMACHY on Envisat (08/2002-04/2012), OMI on Aura (10/2004-current) and GOME-2 aboard MetOp-A, -B and -C (01/2007-current). Data is available in both level 2 (individual satellite soundings) and level 3 (latitude/longitude gridded).

Various versions are available: Level 2 (and research Level 3) data is available by contacting the Group, or via CEDA (www.ceda.ac.uk); official CCI Level 3 [CCI Data Portal, <http://cci.esa.int>]; official C3S Level 3 [C3S Data Store <https://climate.copernicus.eu/>]

The data processed is based on the whole-orbit level 1b versions in Table 1.

Table 1 Data set version

Instrument (Sat)	Level 1 version	Star date	End date	Single sounding resolution ¹
GOME	GDP v4	06/1995	06/2011	
SCIAMACHY	v7.04	08/2002	04/2012	
OMI	V003	10/2004	-	~50x50km
GOME-2(A)	5.3,6.0-6.2,6.3	01/2007	11/2021	Nominal: 160x80km Tandem: 80x80km
GOME-2(B)	5.3,6.0-6.3,7.0,7.1	09/2012	-	Nominal: 160x80km
GOME-2(C)	6.3-7.1	07/2019	-	Nominal: 160x80km

¹ For so figures may differ from nominal spatial resolution of the instrument. This may vary with product version. Nominally, GOME-2 (80x40km) pixels are co-added 2-across x 2-along track, whilst OMI (13x24km) are co-added 4 across x 2 along-track. After the launch of MetOp-B, the swath width of GOME-2(A) was halved (tandem operation mode, 960km), resulting in an associated nominal and co-added pixel resolution.

For some instruments, observations are co-added resulting in the larger single sounding footprint size indicated. This is done to improve the signal to noise of the measurement or the purposes of optimising the retrieval of the tropospheric part of the profile. Whilst the spatial resolution is reduced this results in less ‘noisy’ retrieved tropospheric ozone sub-columns.

Figure 1. Example of output from a GOME-2A orbit of ozone profiles: a) An ozone cross-section on 25 August 2008 retrieved from the Band 2 (final) step for the nadir pixel. The orbit track is also indicated. b) The combined surface and 450hPa (circa 0 and 6km) averaging kernels. c) Relative retrieval error. d) The associated ratio of retrieved to a priori error. (From Miles *et al.*, 2014)

Figure 2. Monthly mean lower tropospheric ozone in 2008 from GOME-2 (not cloud cleared)

The RAL retrieval scheme derives profiles of number density on a set of pressure levels, spaced approximately every 4-6 km in altitude (taken from the SPARC-DI grid). The optimal estimation method is used. Averaging kernels are provided on this basis. It is noted that the vertical resolution of the retrieval is relatively coarse compared to the vertical grid and that tropospheric levels in particular have significant bias towards the assumed *a priori* state. It is therefore important to take account of the characterisation of the retrieval provided by the averaging kernels when comparing these results to other data-sets, particularly where those are more highly vertically resolved.

Figure 1 shows an example of retrieved number density profiles over 1 orbit. Retrieved ozone and ozone error are also provided on levels in volume mixing ratio, in addition to sub-column and sub-column error estimates, which are also shown. Figure 2 shows retrieved lower tropospheric ozone monthly means from GOME-2 in 2008.

The algorithm is sequential retrieval. It uses information from GOME-2 Band 1 initially before performing a surface albedo retrieval in Band 2 and finally an ozone profile retrieval in Band 2 incorporating the information derived from Band 1 as input. The output from both retrievals are included in the product with that from band 1 indicated in the variable name, however it should be highlighted that the output from the Band 1 retrieval is not the algorithm

final solution. Other trace gas spectra are fit as part of the ozone retrieval in order to accurately fit the ozone profile (such as CH₂O and BrO) and their column values are included in the output file, but it should be noted that the chosen fitting window is optimised for ozone rather than these trace gases.

1.3. Use of ozone profiles

We recommend that if users wish to calculate their own sub-columns from the retrieved vmr profiles, or interpolate data between retrieval levels (for example onto a finer vertical grid) this must be performed linearly in vmr pressure. This reflects the relationship between the retrieval levels used in the forward model, which has a finer vertical grid than the retrieval grid.

1.4. Quality Control Criteria

It is recommended that some quality control criteria be applied to the ozone profile data, using parameters also supplied within the NetCDF file:

- ‘cost’ (the total fit cost) is less than 200
- ‘achi’ (the Chi-square test flag) is equal to 1
- ‘sza’ (solar zenith angle) is less than 80°
- ‘o3_tc’ Total column < 1000 (DU)
- ‘ceff’ (effective cloud fraction) is less than 0.2

Tropospheric ozone can have a low bias in the presence of thick cloud (as indicated by ‘cloudf’ (cloud fraction) and/or high cloud ‘cloudp’ (effective cloud top pressure). To cloud screen data it is recommended² that pixels with an effective cloud fraction of greater than or equal to 0.2 are discarded, where effective cloud fraction is calculated by:

$$\text{ceff} = \text{cloudf} * \text{cloud_height_km} / 5.$$

In addition, OMI is affected by a ‘row anomaly’. Only the following pixels should be retained, particularly for full time series analysis to ensure consistent sampling:

- ‘scp’ (Scan position): 9,11,13,15,19,21,43,49,51

Due to the variability³ with time, but generally increasing, for analysis limited to earlier parts of the mission, it may be possible to retain more across-track samples, but user analysis and judgement should be applied.

² For very stringent cloud screening a cloud top pressure of 750hPa or cloud top height of 2km is sometimes used.

³ Some useful information can also be found at: <http://projects.knmi.nl/omi/research/product/rowanomaly-background.php>

1.5. Use of Averaging Kernels

The retrieval is performed in vmr on pressure levels. Versions of the data produced after February 2015 interpolate between forward model levels using linear vmr in linear pressure, and any re-gridding of averaging kernels should use this assumption.

The optimal way of applying the averaging kernels is in their native format accurately re-gridded to the resolution of the profile to which they are to be applied which is also in the same unit. This can however be complicated to do accurately. It is also the case that some user would prefer to directly compare sub-columns and as such the averaging kernels need to be transformed.

RAL can supply an IDL function that can assist in applying profile and sub-column averaging kernels to correlative profiles (such as ozonesondes or model profiles) in a way that is appropriate to the forward model functions and the properties of the retrieved profile. Its functionality is described in Appendix 2 and it is available upon request (remote.sensing@stfc.ac.uk). Otherwise there are a range of variables in the output files derived from this function that can be used.

1.5.1. Use of square sub-column averaging kernels

The NetCDF output files include both the square "ak_sc_sc" and non-square "ak_rsc_tsc" sub-column averaging kernels, as well as the assessed prior contribution (imak_apr_sc) to the sub-column values. It is strongly recommended that users use the non-square AKs (ak_rsc_tsc) applied to their own sub-columns calculated on a matching vertical grid as described in. The non-square averaging kernels have added layers in the troposphere to account of the fact that some information is lost about the way the true averaging kernels are evaluated in the retrieval (levels) in the lowest atmospheric layers. If this is really not possible to do, then see Appendix C.

Higher vertical resolution data (e.g. ozone sonde or model) should be vertically integrated (as indicated above) to the corresponding AK sub-columns to give "sc_o3". These are then converted to a retrieval sub-column equivalent to compare directly with the satellite retrievals by:

$$\text{sonde_sc} = \text{imak_ap_sc} + \text{ak_rsc_tsc} \# \text{sc_o3}$$

2. References

Miles, G. M., Siddans, R., Kerridge, B. J., Latter, B. G., and Richards, N. A. D.: Tropospheric ozone and ozone profiles retrieved from GOME-2 and their validation, Atmos. Meas. Tech. Discuss., 7, 7923-7962, doi:10.5194/amtd-7-7923-2014, 2014. <http://www.atmos-meas-tech-discuss.net/7/7923/2014/amtd-7-7923-2014.html>

Richards, N. A. D., Arnold, S. R., Chipperfield, M. P., Miles, G., Rap, A., Siddans, R., Monks, S. A., and Hollaway, M. J.: The Mediterranean summertime ozone maximum: global emission sensitivities and radiative impacts, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 13, 2331-2345, doi:10.5194/acp-13-2331-2013, 2013. <http://www.atmos-chem-phys.net/13/2331/2013/acp-13-2331-2013.html>

3. Appendix A – Data Format

This section takes as a basis the version fv02xx & fv03xx product format of the RAL ozone scheme. Modifications may be implemented in future in accordance with user needs or to improve consistency with other CCI products.

3.1. Format Description

The format of the Level 2 ozone profile product file from the RAL GOME ozone profile algorithm is NetCDF. The values in all groups are taken from the level 1 or other input data files, or calculated by the program. The file includes output from both the retrieval algorithm and geolocation information, in addition to ancillary information such as surface pressure obtained from ERA-Interimre-analysis.

NCDF Variables			
Dataset name	Data type	Unit	Description
o3_nd	Float array, rank 2	cm-3	Ozone molecular number density Dimension = (n_profiles, n_o3_nd)
o3_vmr	Float array, rank 2	-	Ozone volume mixing ratio, (mole fraction of ozone in air) Dimension = (n_profiles, n_o3_vmr)
o3_error	Float array, rank 2	Percent	Retrieved ozone error Dimension = (n_profiles, n_o3_error)
o3_ap	Float array, rank 2	-	Ozone a priori volume mixing ratio (mole_fraction_of_ozone_in_air) Dimension = (n_profiles, n_o3_ap)
o3_ap_error	Float array, rank 2	Percent	ozone_a_priori_error Dimension = (n_profiles, n_o3_ap_error)
o3_sub_col	Float array, rank 2	Dobson Units	Ozone partial column (mole_content_of_ozone_in_atmosphere_layer)

			Dimension = (n_profiles, n_o3_sub_col)
o3_sub_col_error	Double array, rank 2	Dobson Units	Ozone partial column error (mole_content_of_ozone_in_atmosphere_layer) Dimension = (n_profiles, n_o3_sub_col_error)
o3_ap_sub_col	Double array, rank 2	Dobson Units	Ozone a priori partial column (mole_content_of_ozone_in_atmosphere_layer) Dimension = (n_profiles, n_o3_sub_col)
o3_ap_sub_col_error	Double array, rank 2	Dobson Units	Ozone a priori partial column error (mole_content_of_ozone_in_atmosphere_layer) Dimension = (n_profiles, n_o3_ap_sub_col)
o3_tc	Float array, rank 1	Dobson Units	Total column ozone (atmosphere_mole_content_of_ozone) Dimension = n_profiles
o3_tc_error	Float array, rank 1	Dobson Units	Total column ozone error (atmosphere_mole_content_of_ozone) Dimension = n_profiles
o3_ap_tc_error	Double array, rank 1	Dobson Units	Ozone a priori total column error (atmosphere_mole_content_of_ozone)Dimension = n_profiles
o3_b1_sub_col	Double array, rank 2	Dobson Units	Band 1 ozone partial column (mole_content_of_ozone_in_atmosphere_layer) Dimension = (n_profiles, n_o3_b1_sub_col)
o3_b1_sub_col_error	Double array, rank 2	Dobson Units	Band 1 ozone partial column error (mole_content_of_ozone_in_atmosphere_layer) Dimension = (n_profiles, n_o3_b1_sub_col_error)
o3_b1_tc	Double array, rank 1	Dobson Units	Band 1 total ozone column (atmosphere_mole_content_of_ozone) Dimension = n_profiles
o3_b1_tc_error	Double array, rank 1	Dobson Units	Band 1 total ozone column error (atmosphere_mole_content_of_ozone) Dimension = n_profiles
nit	Long Int array, rank 1	-	Number of iterations Dimension = n_profiles
b1nit	Long int array, Rank1	-	Band 1 number of iterations Dimension = n_profiles
Cost	Float array, rank 1	-	Final cost function value
ncost	Float array, rank 1	-	Normalised final cost function value
b1cost	Float	-	Band 1 cost function value

	array, rank 1		Dimension = n_profiles
aconv	Intarray, rank 1	-	Convergence flag
b1conv	Long int array, rank 1	-	Band 1 convergence flag Dimension = n_profiles
achi	Long int array, rank 2	-	Chi squared flag Dimension = n_profiles
spres	Float, rank 1	hPa	Surface Pressure Dimension = n_profiles
levs	Float, rank 1	hPa	Pressure levels of retrieved ozone profiles Dimension = n_levels
model_levs	Float, rank 1	hPa	Pressure levels for non-square subcolumn AKs (ak_rsc_tsc) Dimension = n_model_levels
lat	Float, rank 1	Degrees north	Latitude of ground pixel centre Dimension = n_profiles
lon	Float, rank 1	Degrees east	Longitude of ground pixel centre Dimension = n_profiles
ll	Float, rank 2	Degrees north/ degrees east	Latitude and longitude of ground pixel corners. [lat1,lon1,lat2,lon2,lat3,lon3,lat4,lon4] Dimensions = (n_profiles x n_ll)
pixno	Long Int, rank 1	-	Orbit ground pixel number ([scan line number * 100]+cross track scan position index) Dimension = n_profiles
sza	Float, rank 1	Degrees	Solar zenith angle Dimension = n_profiles
lza	Float, rank 1	Degrees	Line-of-sight zenith angle Dimension = n_profiles
time	Float, rank 1	Hours	Hours since 00:00.00hrs on date Dimension = n_profiles
scp	Short, rank 1	-	Across trak scan index Dimension = n_profiles
cloudf	Double, Rank 1	-	FRESCO effective cloud fraction
cloudp	Double, Rank 1	hPa	FRESCO cloud top pressure
clouda	Double, Rank 1	-	FRESCO cloud albedo
cloud_ffail	Short,	-	FRESCO cloud fit fail indication

	Rank 1		
cloud_mode	Short, Rank 1	-	FRESCO cloud fit mode
cloud_s6	Double, rank 1	-	Expected scaling of 0-6km sub column due to cloud Dimension = n_profiles
cloud_s12	Double, rank 1	-	Expected scaling of 0-12km sub column due to cloud Dimension = n_profiles
salb	Float, rank 1	-	Retrieved surface albedo Dimension = n_profiles
ring	Float, rank 1	-	Retrieved ring spectrum scaling parameter Dimension = n_profiles
xsect	Float, rank 1	-	Retrieved wavelength shift of absorptions cross sections Dimension = n_profiles
bro	Float, rank 1	-	BrO column average volume mixing ratio Dimension = n_profiles
bro_err	Float, rank 1	-	BrO column average volume mixing ratio error Dimension = n_profiles
no2	Float, rank 1	-	NO ₂ column average volume mixing ratio Dimension = n_profiles
no2_err	Float, rank 1	-	NO ₂ column average volume mixing ratio error Dimension = n_profiles
ch2o	Float, rank 1	-	CH ₂ O column average volume mixing ratio Dimension = n_profiles
ch2o_err	Float, rank 1	-	CH ₂ O column average volume mixing ratio error Dimension = n_profiles
rsf	Float, rank 1	-	Residual spectral pattern scaling factor Dimension = (n_profiles x n_misr)
slit	Float, rank 1	-	Slit function FWHM scaling parameter Dimension = n_profiles
misr	Float, rank 1	nm	Wavelength shift between radiance and irradiance spectra Dimension = (n_profiles x n_misr)
tsurf	Float, rank 1	K	Effective surface temperature Dimensions = (n_profiles, n_tsurf)
sx	Float arr, rank 3	cm-6	Ozone molecular number density solution covariance matrix Dimension = (n_profiles x n_sx_1, n_sx_0)
sn	Float array, rank 3	cm-6	Ozone molecular number density measurement noise covariance matrix Dimension = (n_profiles x n_sn_1 x n_sn_0)

ak	Float array, rank 3	-	Ozone molecular number density averaging kernel matrix Dimension = (n_profiles x n_ak_1, n_ak_2)
ak_sc_sc	Float array, rank 3		Ozone subcolumn averaging kernel matrix (see section on Use of Averaging kernels before using this) Dimension = (n_profiles x n_layers, n_layers)
ak_rsc_tsc	Float array, rank 3		Ozone subcolumn averaging kernel matrix (see section on Use of Averaging kernels before using this) Dimension = (n_profiles x n_layers x n_model_levs)
imak_apr_sc	Float array, rank 2	DU	A priori contribution to estimated sub-column, to be used in association with ak_rsc_tsc in accordance with section on Use of Averaging Kernels Dimension = (n_profiles x n_o3_ap_sub_col)
fm_levs	Float array, rank 2	km	Forward model approximate altitudes according to $Z_{star} = 16(3.0 - \log_{10}(p))$ Dimension = (n_profiles x n_fm_levs)
fm_temperature	Float array, rank 2	K	Forward model temperature profile Dimension = (n_profiles x n_fm_temperature)
fm_pressure	Float array, rank 2	hPa	Forward model pressure profile Dimension = (n_profiles x n_fm_pressure)

4. Appendix B –IDL programme for averaging kernel conversion

The function is called G2_HIRES_AK.pro and is available from georgina.miles@stfc.ac.uk or richard.siddans@stfc.ac.uk.

Please see code header for full description.

Use:

IDL>

IDL> pf=grid_up(tlevs,10) ;increases resolution of vertical P levels 10x for fine representation

IDL> a=g2_hires_ak(ret_vmr, ro3, b1a_ap_vmr, lev, p_surf, ak_nd, pf)

Make high-resolution averaging kernels from data in GOME-2 ncdf file, such that retrieved profiles (vmr and subcolumn) corresponding to a "true" vmr profile defined on a fine grid can be estimated as follows.

The aim is to be able to estimate retrieval as:

$$\begin{aligned} x_{\{vmr\}} &= a'_{\{vmr\}} + A_{\{vmr:f\}} t \\ &= (I - A_{\{vmr:r\}}) a + A_{\{vmr:f\}} t \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} x_{\{sc\}} &= M x_{\{vmr\}} \\ &= a'_{\{sc\}} + M A_{\{vmr:f\}} t \end{aligned}$$

where

$x_{\{vmr\}}$ is retrieved vmr

$x_{\{sc\}}$ is retrieved sub_column

a is a priori (vmr)

$a'_{\{vmr\}}$ is the a priori contribution to the estimated profile = $(I - A_{\{vmr:r\}}) a$

$a'_{\{sc\}}$ is the a priori contribution to the estimated sub-column = $M (I - A_{\{vmr:r\}}) a$

$A_{\{vmr:r\}}$ is the averaging kernel for vmr on retrieval levels, with respect to perturbations on the retrieval grid.

$A_{\{vmr:f\}}$ is the averaging kernel for vmr on retrieval levels, with respect to fine-scale perturbations (on the true profile grid).

M is the matrix which maps the retrieved vmr profile to layer number density in DU

Code returns structure with variables named such that

- `IMAK_APR_VMR`: $a'_{\{sc\}} = M (I - A_{\{vmr:r\}}) a$
- `AK_VMR_F`: $M A_{\{vmr:f\}}$
- `IMAK_APR_SC`: $a'_{\{sc\}} = M (I - A_{\{vmr:r\}}) a$
- `AK_SC_VMR_F`: $M A_{\{vmr:f\}}$
- `PR`: Pressure levels of retrieval grid
- `PF`: Pressure levels of fine (true) grid

So using the structure 'a' passed out of this function, the retrieval can be estimated by:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{estimated_vmr} &= a.\text{IMAK_APR_VMR} + \text{matrix_multiply}(a.\text{AK_VMR_F}, \text{true_profile})^1 \\ \text{estimated_sub_column} &= a.\text{IMAK_APR_SC} + \text{matrix_multiply}(a.\text{AK_VMR_F}, \text{true_profile})^2 \end{aligned}$$

Where `true_profile` is a vector defined on the fine grid. Sub-columns will be in DU.

¹ (above) is considered to be the preferred way of applying averaging kernels to correlative data and will produce the result most faithful to the retrieval. However, if it is not possible or not desired the components for ² are included in the output file so that they may be directly applied to correlative sub-column data (`true_profile` represented as sub-columns) that has been re-gridded or interpolated onto a defined set of levels (`model_levs` – see Appendix A). These are instituted to account for the problem that can arise from the conversion of profile

averaging kernels on a coarse pressure level grid (that have been evaluated in a forward model using perturbations on a fine grid) to the equivalent for a coarse layer grid.

5. Appendix C – Use of square AKs (not recommended)

The non-square averaging kernels have added layers in the troposphere to account of the fact that some information is lost about the way the true averaging kernels are evaluated in the retrieval (levels) in the lowest atmospheric layers. It is strongly recommended they should be used if possible. If this is really not possible to do, there are two ways of using the square averaging kernels.

We have evaluated the impact of using the various forms of the averaging kernels in a 2 year ozonesonde comparison. There are two ways of using the square AKs:

$$1) \text{sonde_sc} = \text{imak_ap_sc} + \text{ak_sc_sc} \# \text{sc_o3}$$

$$2) \text{sonde_sc} = \text{ap_sc} + \text{ak_sc_sc} \# (\text{sc_o3} - \text{ap_sc})$$

From tests involving ozonesonde comparison, we would strongly prefer the use of method 1), as method 2) produces results that don't behave in a way that is very consistent with the retrieval. This is because `imak_ap_sc` was evaluated with more information than is contained in just `ap_sc` (see Appendix 2): `Imak_ap_sc` was derived from the vmr profile and then transformed onto the sub-column grid.